

DEVELOPMENT OF LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF CADRE AS A CURRENT SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article will reveal the difference between the leader and the manager in the development of their leadership qualities based on the resources collected as a result of studying the issues of improving their leadership qualities in the training of reserve cadre and the directors of preschool educational organizations.*

Keywords: *leader, authority, manager, cadre, reform, manager, govern, head, civil servants, personnel.*

Leadership research has gone through several stages. The scientists of the first stage are characterized by attempts to determine the characteristics that an effective leader should possess. However, this theory did not give the expected results in practice. Research shows that leaders with the same success were characterized by different characteristics. In addition, the list of leadership characteristics is very long, and in practice, no person can fully possess these aspects. Cadre is not just someone who performs the command. Looking at the experience of developed countries, whether it be South Korea, Singapore, or Malaysia, one of the main reasons why they were promoted from a third-level economic state to a first-level one was staff policy. The cadre is not the only one that conveys the isotope "down". He is the one who can add something to him, offer a solution, and correctly interpret the "top" that he could not reach. Then he is the person between the leadership and the nation. Therefore, he would have served as a bridge between these two communities.

Leaders in the organizations have great authority. Although power can be achieved through force, deception, or accident, it may not always lead to the leadership. But, on the contrary, leadership is a means of achieving power. Research of the nature of power according to European traditions associated with N. Machiavelli and his famous work "The Prince" Machiavelli believed that power is especially important in the transition from one state to another, as human thought is also reshaped in this process. These processes create resistance, and power is necessary to overcome this resistance.

Leadership is an authority that is not based on the usage of force. No one knows where the leaders come from, but things start developing as soon as the leaders arise in the organizations. At the moment, there is no doubt that leadership is one of the main organizers of the business.

Leadership in quality management systems is also viewed as the system's primary guiding mechanism. The literature on quality management also emphasizes the need for leadership for all components of the organization's system.

Who is the manager? A manager is a provident and efficient person. And by the 21st century, a new term began to be used – the term "leaders".

A leader is a person who works not only for the result but also instills a sense of satisfaction in both the civil servants serving in that company and the people using the organization's service.

For example, let's call the governor a leader. It should create conditions in its territory so that both the service and the use of it feel comfortable.

Today we all need to understand one thing:

Citizens of the 21st century cannot be guided by 20th-century management methods.

Because today we live in the era of globalization, we are in the process of violent changes.

Citizens, on the other hand, pay special attention to each case. When making decisions on problems related to society, it is of course also important to ensure the participation of citizens. When will a citizen be grateful? When he feels that he is a participant in the reforms that are being implemented. When does a citizen feel invulnerable? When his will is reflected in that reform.

What should be the result of the reform? As a result, someone's problem must be solved. The worldview of our people is markedly different from four to five years ago. People's demands and needs are changing. This means that the style of work of each employee must change depending on this. A civil servant from four years ago, with his services and worldview at that time, cannot work now. This is not allowed, firstly, by the leadership, secondly, by the people, and thirdly, by the media.

In order for people to see a result today, we are required to think non-standardly, with creativity, and to take a special approach to the issue through systematic thinking. Hence, our change is narrow.

What causes change? Change begins, first of all, with our thinking. We can alter our thinking and approach to work, and the results will be unexpected. A simple example is that the Korean miracle was the joint transformation of people's and civil servants' attitudes towards some problems.

To improve the efficiency of the activities of state authorities and governing bodies, first of all, management leaders in general are required to have a high level of leadership and leadership character among all personnel. In recent years, the implementation of high-level reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan in all areas has increased the need for qualified and modern executive personnel. This, in turn, requires searching for ways to solve this problem.

R. Hotamov believes that analyses and observations confirm that when there are a lot of common-sense, inquisitive, and enterprising employees around the manager, the environment in such a team is also healthy, and the working mood of employees is also high. Leadership spirituality is an important factor in strengthening the effectiveness of activities and the spiritual and moral aspects of the team, and the talent of the leader ensures the success of the team.

According to the research made by scientists, it has been proven that 80% of team achievements depend on the leadership organization and the remaining 20% on the potential of only employees.

The following spiritual criteria for leaders are central to the formation of a mature identity:

First of all, each leader must be first and foremost open-minded, clean-hearted, intelligent, and have high potential. It is impossible to lead others to achieve the goals of the first goal when honest, confident, and open-minded people are not chosen.

Secondly, the leader must honestly serve his people, who have brought themselves up and raised themselves, who are worthy of a high position of confidence, and who always have a deep sense of immense responsibility. He should not forget that he is responsible to the people and to the land. On the principle of our president that "The nation shouldn't serve the public authorities,

but public authorities should serve the nation", it is necessary that it become the main rule in the activities of leaders in all branches.

Thirdly, the leader should rely on experienced, knowledgeable specialists of the work under his hands and draw conclusions based on the opinions of the team. Today's leader is required to know all areas well, to be aware of the sciences of economics, information technology, law, politics, and spirituality, and to master new innovative technologies. Therefore, he must be constantly sought after, exalted in his knowledge and skills, and have a new way of thinking.

Fourth, the leader's style of work and the decisions he makes should serve the effectiveness of the activity. It is important that the leader abandons the methods of administrative commandment and does not give in to formalism. To look good at someone, to brag, is ostentatious and has only negative consequences.

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In addition, it is important that the leader has his own idea and program of action, starting others along the same path, and uniting them around a single goal.

In relations with employees, a leader should inspire admiration for himself in others with his worldview, culture, and treatment, and keep in mind the interconnection of leadership and spirituality factors.

It is necessary for the leader to be demanding of compliance with the requirements of regulatory documents by his subordinates, to set an example for them in respect of high professional skills, legality, and adherence to the oath, to stimulate their initiative and aspirations, and to be uncompromising towards employees who violate service discipline and are prone to other negative situations.

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